

Paper: On the Origin of Questions in Process Mining Projects

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Additional Materials

In this document we provide details about the data collection and analysis of the interview study presented in this paper. The materials include details on the **Participants' Selection**, **Participants' Demographics**, **Interview Guide** and **Coding Examples**.

Participants' Selection

Inclusion Criteria

The goal of this paper is to gain an understanding of **how are questions developed within process mining projects?**

Since existing process mining methodologies and published case studies often do not reveal the dynamics of question formulation and development due to a reporting bias, meaning that they only write about a specific question and the related findings, we focus on learning from people having experience with process mining analyses.

For this paper, we consider the following inclusion criteria:

1. Having analyzed at least two real-life event logs over the two years prior to the study;
2. Being knowledgeable of at least one among bupaR, Celonis, Disco, pm4py, ProM, i.e., the process mining tools available for the process mining task.
3. Having participated in at least two process mining projects having the goal to analyze process data for a customer.

These requirements allow us to ensure that our participants have both general process mining experience and practical experience with process mining projects. Moreover, they allow us to focus on experts and include participants with different backgrounds (e.g., academics and practitioners) and working in different areas (e.g., consulting, analytics, education).

Participants' Demographics

We collected demographic characteristics and self-reported experience and expertise in process mining and related fields through a demographic questionnaire. **Table 1** shows a summary of the collected information for the 33 participants selected for the study presented in this paper.

P#	Sector	Current Role	Experience (yrs)		Expertise		#Projects	#Tools	#Logs
			Process Mining	Data Science	Process Mining	Process Analytics			
3	National Laboratory	Senior R&D Staff	3	> 10	Good	Average	2 - 5	2	> 10
5	Consumer Goods	Process Analyst	2.5	Up to 1	Average	Average	2 - 5	1	6 - 10
6	Freelance	Process Mining Consultant	2	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
7	Academia	Full Professor	10	6-10	Advanced	Average	6 - 10	3	> 10
8	Academia	Assistant Professor	10	4-5	Advanced	Good	2 - 5	2	> 10
9	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	3.5	1-3	Good	Good	> 20	2	6 - 10
11	Freelance	Business Analyst	8	> 10	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	4	6 - 10
12	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Good	2 - 5	4	2 - 5
14	Enterprise Software	Product Manager/Engineer	3	1-3	Good	Good	10 - 20	1	> 10
15	Academia	Assistant Professor	6	6-10	Good	Average	2 - 5	3	> 10
16	Academia	PhD Student	4	None	Average	Average	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
17	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	4	1-3	Good	Average	10 - 20	1	> 10
18	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	4	> 10
19	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	4	> 10
23	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	1	Up to 1	Average	Average	2 - 5	2	2 - 5
24	Enterprise Software	Analytics Product Management	3	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	1	6 - 10
25	Food Processing	Process Analyst	4	> 10	Good	Good	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
26	Packaging	Digital Project Manager	7	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	1	2 - 5
27	Financial	Process Mining Analyst	1	1-3	Average	Average	2 - 5	5	6 - 10
28	Academia	Full Professor	4	> 10	Good	Good	2 - 5	4	> 10
29	Academia	PhD Student	6	6-10	Good	Average	2 - 5	5	> 10
30	Academia	Full Professor	10	1-3	Average	Good	2 - 5	5	2 - 5
31	Telecommunications	Principal Business Consultant	2	> 10	Basic	Good	2 - 5	1	> 10
32	Academia	PhD Student	2	1-3	Average	Basic	2 - 5	2	2 - 5
33	Constructions	Operational Excellence Lead	3	4-5	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	1	> 10
34	Government	Consultant	10	> 10	Good	Good	6 - 10	2	2 - 5
35	Insurance	Business Analyst	2	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	1	2 - 5
36	Academia	PhD Student	6	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	3	6 - 10
37	Insurance	Operational Excellence Lead	5	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	> 20	1	> 10
38	Academia	Full Professor	8	4-5	Good	Good	6 - 10	4	6 - 10
39	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	10 - 20	5	2 - 5
40	Academia	Senior Researcher	16	4-5	Advanced	Advanced	> 20	4	> 10
41	Academia	PhD Student	7	6-10	Good	Advanced	2 - 5	2	6 - 10

Table 1: Overview of the 33 selected participants.

P#: is the original participant ID assigned during the data collection (P1, P2, P4, P10, P13, P20, P21, P22 have been excluded since they did not meet the inclusion criteria defined for this paper). **Sector:** the sector to which the participant's affiliation/company belongs. **Current Role:** the participant's job role at the time of the data collection. **Experience (yrs):** years of experience in process mining and data science or analytics. **Expertise:** expertise in process mining and process analytics; a Likert scale with values Novice, Basic, Average, Good and Advanced was used. **#Projects:** the number of process mining projects having the goal of analyzing process data for a customer/company the participant took part in. **#Tools:** the number of process mining tools that the participant can use comfortably. **#Logs:** the number of event logs analyzed in the past two years. **#Tools, #Logs and #Projects** are related to our inclusion criteria.

Overall, the participants selected for the study presented in this paper have an average process mining experience of 5.55 years. They also reported experience in neighboring fields, such as data science (32/33) and business intelligence (30/33), with 16 people reporting 6 years or more of experience in those fields. Regarding self-reported expertise, six participants reported having "Average" process mining expertise, sixteen reported having "Good" process mining expertise, and ten reported having "Advanced" process mining expertise.

Saturation

We stopped collecting data when we achieved data saturation (Saunders, 2018), i.e., we noticed that answers were repeating across interviews and that patterns in the work practices were starting to emerge.

Example of Saturation.

The two statements below remark that without domain knowledge there is a risk to conduct analyses that are trivial or not interesting.

«I mean, we are typically as researchers, not the domain experts. So you tend to come up with trivial things or you don't have a clear goal in mind. » (p18)

«... I understand a lot of the of the business process with business people and it avoids me to ask silly questions or to put down silly hypotheses. » (p34)

Interview Guide

(T): To be asked referring to the process mining task; (G): To be asked referring to general work practices

ACTIVITIES, TARGET ARTIFACTS and USE of ARTIFACTS

- Can you briefly summarize the main steps of your analysis today and explain why you worked in this way? (T)
- Would you always follow the same steps in practice? (G)
- What information did you aim to gather during the analysis? Why? (T)
- Would you always focus on gathering the same information in practice or does that change from case to case? (G)
- How did you use the provided artifacts during the analysis? Why were they useful? (T)

GOALS

- Can you summarize the main goals of your analysis today? (T)
- Do you always work with these goals in mind in practice? (G)
- Do you always have clear analysis goals or objectives in practice? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that the analyses you conduct in practice are exploratory? By exploratory we mean that you spend time refining research questions, generating new questions for the analysis.

STRATEGIES, START and TERMINATION CRITERIA

- Did you follow any specific strategy (plan of action to achieve a certain goal) when trying to answer the questions today? (T)
- Did your analysis approach change during the analysis? If so, how? (T)
- Would you follow the same approach in practice, with other event logs? (G)
- How did you decide where to start your analysis from? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually choose where to start your analysis from? (G)
- How did you decide that it was time to stop the analysis? Did you follow any criteria? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually decide that it is time to stop the analysis? (G)

CHALLENGES

- Is there anything that you found challenging during the task today? (T)
 - And in general, what do you think are the biggest challenges of process mining? (G)
 - On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that good tool knowledge helps to overcome process mining challenges? (G)
 - Do you think that combining different process mining tools is an opportunity for the analysis or do you think it is too complicated/not needed? (G)
 - Taking a look at process mining, where do you think there is more need for methodological or operational support? (G)
-

Coding Examples

Here we show examples from our final coding round. Our coding covers different themes capturing different aspects revolving around the question development process, including *starting points and endpoints* of a process mining project, different kinds of *analysis* and *analysis strategies*.

Theme	Code	Example Statements
Start	Question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - So it's always research-oriented, actually, like it's always like with answering a question in mind, ok, in my line of work (p14) - Um, where to start my analysis from? Well, based on the question. (p15) - But the large majority are really concrete often, not always, but often very concrete questions from the auditor. So, can we find this in this kind of documents or tool? (p25)
	No question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - But in practice, what I have done so far we didn't have special questions, unfortunately. (p6) - I'm not so used to having a concrete question because even the industry ones were less of a consultancy or more research-focused analysis and then usually you first need to inspire the stakeholders about what they could have as a question. (p12) - Usually they don't ask questions, but they say "this is our data." We usually have these projects where people still have limited knowledge of what is possible. (p39)
End	Not a process mining question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If your goals are very specific, then. Yeah, you might not even go to a process model or process mining tool, you would just go for SQL (p19)
	Question answered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - So, if I could reach an answer that is satisfactory from my point of view and all the questions have been answered from the process owner, then I could send them back the results (p41)
	New question generated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I try to get answers. Usually these answers open new questions. (p34)
Analysis	Raw data analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yeah, because, I mean, basically, for me, like I really want to understand, I really want to understand, like the sort of data structure first (p24) - There is always some exploration. I mean, you have to get your hands dirty. I mean, I usually spent one or two days working with dirty ways with the event logs. I mean, you have to get familiar with particularities, like missing values or like unexpected transitions or things that don't look familiar to the eye. So, I always start with this. (p30) - I would check to try to learn much more from the raw data before even going to the map. (p37)
	Exploratory analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When you have the customer or the stakeholder with you, you start doing some interactive process mining tasks like looking at a dotted chart together, explaining how the dotted chart works and then seeing how the partner identifies things that he or she knows. And, well, I think the explorative part is typically first and and it's a smooth transition to the answering of the research question. (p15) - My usual goals are first try to understand the data that we have and after that, make hypotheses to answer different questions. (p27) - If I don't have any starting point, then is more difficult. I try to apply some techniques to find some value for the analysis, like some bottleneck or something that looks strange that would be discussed with the process owner. And then, my analysis is freer and I start applying all the possible techniques until I find something interesting. (p41)
	Pre-defined analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Afterward, I try to take a look at the basic questions and basic assumptions that come up in process analysis in my experience. These people I talk to ask always to look at the standard KPIs, next throughput time. Or non-compliant processes. (p23) - Yes, there is a path that this will always be there. I mean, I will always look at the map. I always look to the popular transitions. I always look at data attributes for missing values. Ok, I will always look at some performance elements. (p30) - Celonis is a time in the market and I think it's currently also the biggest player; they have a certain set of standard hypotheses and analyses behind. So this makes life easier, so you don't start with an empty piece of paper. (p33)

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Internal benchmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - And out of that 20%, the majority is about when a benchmark, good and bad, I also want to see the good side of it, but still I want to fix the bad country. (p9) - So, it usually starts with the pain point, and what we do is, for example, benchmarking. [...] or so, where you have like different activities, purchasing organizations or vendors or customers or production plans, and from that, you can then see, "Ok, this plant is really doing well. So, most of the...orders are produced on time and this plan is really bad comparison", and then you would want to find out "What is this plan doing, doing good in comparison to the other?". (p17)
Best practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - And so actually, what what we try to propose is that you don't see these deviations as something that should be rejected or prevented, but more of something that should be studied further and to identify so that you can use them to improve your processes. (p16) - ...we look at the positive cases is to see whether there's a gap in the way they work. So, there are some best practices missing. So, you know, the clients we're working with we noticed that they didn't do a step that we see a lot of phone companies do. And we said, "look this would be a good idea for you." So, yeah, you can look for improvements. (p31)
Heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - So, if the question was specific about a specific pattern, I will not go for Pareto, I will go for the pattern. (p7) - I mean, the most frequent variants are in general the ones that are used most, where you have more flesh on the bone, and yeah, I use this 80-20 Pareto principle at the beginning, because if you start to have a look at all the variants, often you have hundreds or thousands of variants, you get lost. (p26)
Analysis Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - So, one thing I find important more than collecting data is always the link with the questions itself. So, I will go for a top-down analysis like "these are the questions, what are the data that support my hypothesis to answer that question?"(p7) - So, I'm immediately looking at those event attributes because they were or they seem to be the most central data object for the guiding question (p18)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I would also do some exploring by myself, because it's always nice to really understand the data also from perspectives or aspects that are not really relevant to questions itself to just get the full context of trying to get a full context. (p18) - ...kind of more like you're looking for an answer to the question, but anything you keep an eye open for, things that stand out. (p19) - I'm always curious to find out what is happening around the process on around the question or trying to capture to generate hypotheses and test them. So, in my practice, I always explore beyond the question. (p30)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, actually, what I did is I make a preliminary hypothesis. Then I refine this hypothesis while I was exploring, especially in the first step, while I was exploring, I was refining this hypothesis. (p7) - then, we always try to see if we can identify three hypotheses together with the customer, say, ok, let's let's have three things that we should examine. (p11) - ...iterating upon and creating like looking at picking out hypothesis right from the question... (p12)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - You check that the hypothesis makes sense in a secondary step, once the data is already been explored. (p7) - Then I create something that allows me to reject or validate this hypothesis (p12) - If I have time and I want to verify my hypotheses, I would then export subsets of data to event logs, which I use in PM4Py to further confirm my hypothesis or to give a statistic in how many cases this is valid and how many cases this is not true. (p39)

References

(Saunders, 2018) Saunders, B., Sim, J., Kingstone, T. et al. Saturation in qualitative research: exploring its conceptualization and operationalization. Qual Quant 52, 1893–1907 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-017-0574-8>